

ISic3099

I.Sicily inscription 3099

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331424

1. [μετὰ] τὴν ὑπα [τίαν]
2. [τοῦ δεσπότης] ἢ [μῶν]
3. [Θεοδ]οσίου τὸ [ζ'κ(αὶ) Παλ]-
4. [λαδίου]υ λαμ [προτ.]
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645447

PHI 331424

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 36.0871

Ferrua, A 1982-1983. Le iscrizioni datate della Sicilia paleocristiana. *Kokalos*. 28-29: 3-29. At 15 no.43

Orsi, P. 1895. Insigne epigrafe del cimitero di S. Giovanni in Siracusa. *Römische Quartalschrift für christliche Alterthumskunde und für Kirchengeschichte*. 9: 299-308. At 480 no.153

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3099. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388129>